

Diet and Foraging of Herring and Great Black-backed Gulls On Tuckernuck and Muskeget Islands, Massachusetts in 2016

A Report to Nantucket Biodiversity Initiative

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Abstract: We studied diet and foraging behavior of Herring and Great-blacked Gulls at Tuckernuck and Muskeget Islands during May-July 2016. We had anticipated that the inshore fishery for Long-finned Squid (*Loligo peali*), which extends to within 3 NM of the beach at Tuckernuck, was to be curtailed or restricted to waters much farther offshore in 2016, and if this had occurred, would have yielded a convenient comparison with our work in 2015. The fishery was not curtailed in 2016, so multiple trawlers worked within 3 NM of the beach throughout the period of our 2016 study, and we were unable to make the anticipated comparison. Of 89 Great Black-backed Gull chicks whose diet we sampled in June, 11 had food in their crops, and of these 11 samples, 6 contained squid. The 5 others contained lady crabs and unidentified fish fragments. Of 12 adult Herring Gulls sampled in late May, 4 contained fresh sand lance. Our GPS tracking of Herring Gulls revealed that birds traveled 3-5 NM offshore, to areas populated with squid trawlers. Nevertheless, the diet samples we obtained contained primarily sand lance.

Introduction

Populations of Herring and Great Black-backed Gulls have fluctuated dramatically since their appearance in Massachusetts during the early 20th century (Veit and Petersen

1993; Black 2016, Nisbet et al. 2013). Much of the fluctuation in Massachusetts, as elsewhere in the United States, has reflected the growth and then decline of food supplies provided at garbage dumps and around commercial fishery operations (Barrett et al. 2007; Camphuysen 2013). On islands off Nantucket, numbers of breeding gulls reached a peak in 1980-1990, and have since declined; the decline has been especially steep after the cessation of open dumping the Nantucket landfill in the mid 1990s. In the few years following the change in dumping practices, the impact on locally nesting Great Black-backed Gulls was severe: the entire Muskeget colony experienced complete reproductive failure, with most chicks dying in the first week after hatching (RRV, pers. obs.). Herring Gulls were also impacted but they seemed more capable of catching wild prey, compared to the Great Black-backed Gulls which seemed more dependent on garbage. Since the late 1990s, numbers of all gulls nesting on the Nantucket Islands have continued to decline, and Herring Gulls have increased in proportion to Great Black-backed Gulls. During this period, though, both species have managed to raise substantial numbers of young, i.e. the die offs of the 1990s have not persisted.

Nevertheless, seeing that the major fluctuations in populations of these birds has been substantially driven by food supply, it seems worth asking what is driving reproductive success of gulls now, after the majority of the scavenged prey (garbage, fishery waste) has disappeared. To this end, we sought to document the current diet of these birds, and also to use a pilot study to determine where the breeding adults go to capture prey to feed their young.

Methods

This is a second year of an intensive study of gull diet on Tuckernuck and Muskeget Islands (Black 2016), and we used similar methods. We sampled diet from chicks only. Our procedure was to walk through the colonies, at time intervals of > 3 days to prevent too-frequent sampling of any one chick, and picked up chicks in order to band them. In the process of banding chicks, the ones that had recently been fed would regurgitate right away and we weighed all such regurgitations and either identified the prey items immediately or brought them back to the lab for identification. To track the foraging of Herring Gulls (we only had sufficient gps receivers to track Herring Gulls this year), we caught adults using noose carpets placed on 3 egg clutches in nests, and affixed the gps receivers to the central rectrices using friction tape. We retrapped all tagged gulls with a week of deployment and removed the tags. No birds were harmed during the course of tag deployment.

Results

We banded 89 Great Black-backed Gull chicks and 15 herring Gull chicks in 2016. Of the 89 Great Black-backed chicks, we obtained 11 food samples. Of the eleven, 6 contained Long-finned Squid and the other 5 contained Lady Crab and unidentified fish, likely trawler bycatch. All four of the samples from adult Herring Gulls contained freshly caught sand lance. I have appended our (more extensive) data from 2015 to give some context for the 2016 samples (Figure 1). Since the squid fishery did not change between years, the diet data do not show dramatic differences, albeit with small samples in 2016.

Figure 1.) Diet data from Tuckernuck and Muskeget in 2015 from Black (2016). Note the preponderance of squid and sand lance in the diet of both species of gulls.

Tracking of adult Herring Gulls in May 2016 showed that these birds (n = 10) focused their foraging effort about 3-5 NM offshore from Tuckernuck, both to the south in the Atlantic and to the north in Nantucket Sound. Both these locations are plainly visible from land on Tuckernuck and we could see numbers of trawlers working these areas for squid during the time that the gulls were carrying gps receivers (Figure 2).

Figure 2.) GPS tracks of adult Herring Gulls tagged on Tuckernuck Island, 20-30 May 2016. Each color is a single bird.

Discussion

We had two main objectives in this project. The first was to evaluate whether the change in squid fishing regulation would impact the diets of the gulls we were studying. Since the regulatory changes were not implemented, we cannot address this objective, except to say that in both years Great Black-backed Gulls were fairly clearly focused upon squid, and multiple (~20) squid trawlers were present. As some of the squid the gulls caught were much smaller (2- 5 cm total length) we think it likely that gulls were not only catching trawler discards but also catching free swimming squid from the many large squid schools present. We suspect that gulls following groups of feeding Gray Seals may be doing so in order to catch squids (and sand lance and other fishes) driven to the surface by seals. The tracking data on Herring Gulls similarly indicates their interest in attending trawlers to scavenge squids and any fishes bycaught in squid trawls. However, both Herring and Great Black-backed Gulls in both 2015 and 2016 also caught large (>30 g) boluses of very fresh sand lance, that certainly did not come out of a squid trawl. This is of interest both because it indicates gulls have “learned” to catch wild prey after the closing of garbage dumps, and also because in the past (Veit and Petersen 1993) very large numbers of a broad diversity of seabirds have seemingly depended upon this resource that at times reaches superabundant levels.

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